

Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Program on Knowledge of First aid Management of Minor Injuries Among Mothers of Kinder Garten Students of SPA Campus Bhauri, Bhopal

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ABSTRACT

Quasi- Experimental one group pretest –post test design was conducted to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program on first aid management of minor injuries among mothers of kindergarten children at Bhauri, 60 samples were selected by simple random sampling technique and assessed their knowledge score by structured questionnaire. Structured teaching program on first aid management of minor injuries were given .After seven days of the post test were conducted by using same questionnaire. There was significant improvement in knowledge score and practices related to prevention of minor abrasions at 0.01 level. Out of 60 mothers 3.3%(2) had adequate knowledge, 13.4%(8) had moderately adequate knowledge, 83.3%(50) had inadequate knowledge score in pre-test. 1.66 %(1) had inadequate knowledge, 86.7 %(52) had adequate knowledge, 11.64 %(7) had moderately adequate knowledge in post test..there is no significant difference between demographic variables of pre test and post test scores of knowledge and knowledge on practice.

KEY WORDS: assess, first aid, knowledge

INTRODUCTION:

Adequate knowledge required for handling injuries in mothers of kindergarten students without hospital setting (home or site of accidents) may not be sufficient as formal first aid training is not given to them . Imparting knowledge on first aid management could help in preventing injuries and also to deal with the injuries caused more effectively^[1]. Minor injuries in children are common these injuries can result in scar formation which could adversely affect even their personality. Knowledge in first aid management prevents such instances to great extend.

Need of the study:

From the Indian context it can be said that all children have experienced minor injuries due to fall. The recent studies have revealed that knowledge level of parents or even the teachers to deal with these

injuries are inadequate and some cases have resulted in disabilities. Adequate knowledge on this management of injuries can help the parents to deal with them and also to take a decision for secondary assistance from the hospital. The knowledge on the reasons for fall and the nature of injuries resulting from such fall will help to wear protective gear and educate the children on the consequences of fall. Awareness in the parents will enable them to give timely first aid or required treatment effectively^[2].

Statement of Problem: A study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge of first aid management of minor injuries among mothers of kinder garten students residing SPA Campus Bhauri at Bhopal.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To assess the pre existing knowledge score on first aid management among the mothers of kinder garden students (children below 5 years of age).
- 2.To evaluate the effectiveness structured teaching program by comparing pretest &post test knowledge score.
- 3.To find out the association between pretest

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knowledge score of first aid management and selected demographic variables.

Hypotheses:

H₁: There will be difference between pre and post test level of score on knowledge of first aid management among the mothers of kinder garten students at the level of $p < 0.05$.

H₂: There will be significant association between knowledge of first aid management among mothers of kinder garten students and selected Demographic variables at the level of $p < 0.05$.

Research Methodology:

Research approach : Evaluative approach

Research Design : Quasi- experimental research design

Setting : SPA campus

Population : Mothers of kinder garden children in SPA campus

Sampling technique : Simple random sampling technique

Sample size : 60

Inclusion criteria: The mothers of kinder garten students are willing for the study. Mothers are available at the time of the study.

Exclusion criteria: Mothers are not willing for the study; **Research Tool:** Structured questionnaire.

Data Collection Procedure:

The Investigator introduced herself to the mothers and explained the significance of the study. Consent was obtained from them after explaining them the purpose of the study. The questions are administered and responses are obtained and recorded in pre test and 45 minutes Structured teaching program was imparted to the group. After seven days of structured teaching program the post test conducted.

RESULTS:

Section-I: Distribution of demographic variables among mothers. Majority of the mothers (33%) were studied up to Primary school, followed by High school (14%) and above (3%) and only few of them (50%) were Illiterate. Only few of the students' fathers (5%) were labourer while Majority of them (59%) was Farmer, followed by Businessman (28%) and Employee (8%). Only few of the mothers (2%) were employee while majority of them (40%) were home maker, followed by Labourer (56%) and remaining (4%) were doing business.

Section-II: Distribution of level of knowledge and knowledge on practice related to prevention of minor injuries among mothers in pre test and post test. Out of

60 mothers Very few parents (10%) had received knowledge relating to first aid from their teachers, followed by friends (12%), health professionals (12%), Family members (27%), and mass media (39%). Over all knowledge on minor injuries and knowledge on practices indicated 68% had poor knowledge and 32% had inadequate knowledge in pre-test.

Majority of the respondents (70%) had average knowledge and remaining (30%) had good knowledge in the post test as compared to the pre test where majority (68%) had poor knowledge and remaining (32%) had average knowledge. The mean post test knowledge score ($X_2 = 22.10$) was apparently higher than the mean pre test knowledge score ($X_1 = 11.12$) suggesting that Structured teaching program was effective in increasing the knowledge of the students on first aid.

Table: Comparing of Pretest & Post test knowledge score.

Pre-test knowledge score			Post-test knowledge score		
Poor	Average	Good	Poor	Average	Good
68%	32%	0	0%	70%	30%

DISCUSSION:

The study revealed that out of 60 mothers 68% had poor knowledge and 32% had Average knowledge in pretest. 70% had average knowledge and 30% had good knowledge on knowledge score on first aid management among the mothers of kinder garden students. There is a significant improvement in knowledge and knowledge practices related to prevention of minor injuries at 0.01 levels and there is no significant difference between demographic variables of pretest and post test scores of knowledge and knowledge on practice. Research hypothesis was accepted. This result clearly shows that was useful in improving the knowledge of mothers on first aid for selected accidents and emergencies^[3]. Therefore it was confirmed that structured teaching program was an effective strategy to improve the knowledge level of the mothers.

The findings have its support from the following studies:

According to a study on effectiveness of planned teaching program on first aid among 60 high school students of Udupi, India, it showed that there was a significant difference between the mean pre test and post test knowledge scores of the High School

children for selected accidents and emergencies ($t_{60}=13.41, p<0.05$)^[4].

A quasi-experimental study was adopted to assess the effect of structured teaching program on First Aid Management and Emergency Care of burn patients among 60 staff nurses working in selected hospitals of Ludhiana, Punjab. The study revealed that the maximum pre-test knowledge score of staff nurses in control group (56%) and experimental group (60%) was good⁵. Maximum post-test knowledge score in control group was good (52%) while in experimental group, it was excellent (96%) .

Recommendation: On the basis of finding of the study, the following recommendation is made for the future research study^[6]. A similar study can be replicated with broader content area on accidents and emergencies. A comparative study can be conducted between urban and rural schools and college. A similar study can be replicated with different demographic variables. A similar study can be replicated with different population^[7].

Implication: Immediate first aid during emergency situation helps to sustain the life and prevent complication. Training program in these areas will help to develop the skills of the community. In this context, health professional especially nurses has a major role in training the community, by using the most effective and simplest method. The nursing curriculum should lay more emphasis on first aid. The students posted in the community health, school health, hospital should be able to give education to the people regarding first aid.

CONCLUSION:

There is a significant difference in pre and post level of knowledge regarding first aid management minor injuries. This showed that the planned teaching program was effective in increasing the knowledge of mothers regarding first aid management of minor injuries.

Ethical Clearance:

Prior permission was obtained from the Registrar of SPA .informed consent was obtained from the samples .confidentiality and privacy of the data was maintained.

Source of fund: Self.

Conflict of interest: None.

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